

Decarboxylation of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid: Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (0.3 g) was refluxed with HCl (25 ml) for 2 h. It was then extracted with chloroform and the chloroform layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove unconverted acid. The resulting solid after the removal of chloroform, was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to yield diphenylamine, m.p. 56° (m.m.p. with authentic sample and ir spectra confirmed its identity).

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance. Thanks are also due to the Principal, Durgapur Women's College and authorities of Visva-Bharati for facilities.

References

1. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Fortsch. Chem. Org. Naturst.*, 1977, 34, 279; D. P. CHAKRABORTY, K. O. DAS, B. P. DAS and B. K. CHAUDHURY, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1975, 38, 1.
2. K. SAKANO and S. NAKAMURA, *J. Antibiot.*, 1980, 33, 688; L. M. RICH and K. R. SCOT, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, 13, 308; A. A. ASSCHU, L. HUMBER and J. KOMLOSSY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1975, 19, 791; J. G. PERCA and S. M. ALBONICO, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, 13, 327; A. MOORADION, P. DUPONT, A. G. HALAAR, M. D. ACETO and J. PAL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, 20, 487; D. N. CHOWDHURY and B. P. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1979, 48, 344; A. SHORB, F. ANWAR, R. S. KAPIL, S. R. POPLI, P. R. DUA and B. N. DHAWAN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1973, 16, 425.
3. B. CHOUHDURY and B. P. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1983, 52, 1130.
4. K. A. GREILMAN, G. M. SHERMAN and H. LINSCHITZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 1881.
5. W. CARRUTHERS, *Chem. Commun.*, 1966, 272.
6. A. ISLAM, P. BHATTACHARYA and D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 587.
7. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1984, 47, 49.
8. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *Planta Medica*, 1980, 39, 97.
9. K. H. BÜCHEL, "Chemistry of Pesticides", Wiley, New York, 1983, p. 157.
10. I. HEILBORN, A. H. COOK, H. M. BURBURY and D. H. HEY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 4th. ed., Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1965, Vol. 3, p. 1272.

Synthesis of 4-Benzoyl-3,5-diarylisoxazoles

J. T. GANVIR and V. N. INGLE*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 26 May 1987, revised 4 August 1988,
accepted 1 September 1988

3-Benzoyl-2-aryl chromones (1a–e) have been synthesised by the oxidative cyclisation of the corresponding 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-arylacrylophenones¹. 1a–e on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride yielded the isoxazoles 2a–e. Chincholkar and Jamode² reported the synthesis of some isoxazoles (2) by the interaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and 3-aroil-2-aryl chromones (1). In the present communication we

have extended the reaction to other chromones (1a–e) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride leading to the isoxazoles (2a–e).

3-Benzoyl-2-(4-chlorophenyl) chromone (1a) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acetic acid for 1 h, and the resulting clear solution on dilution with water gave a white granular solid (2a) which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 145°; it was soluble in dilute NaOH and gave intense violet colour with FeCl₃; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 670 (CO), 3 206 (OH), 1 530 (C=N) and 760 cm⁻¹ (isoxazole); δ (CDCl₃) 10.2 (1H, s, OH), 6.84–7.58 (14H, m, ArH). On the basis of these data it was assigned the structure of isoxazole (2a).

On extending the reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride to other chromones (1b–e) the corresponding isoxazoles (2b–e) were synthesised (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-BENZOYL-3-ARYL-5-(2-HYDROXYPHENYL)ISOXAZOLES (2)*

Compd. no.	R ¹	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	4-Cl-Phenyl	145	50
2b	3-NO ₂ -Phenyl	161	46
2c	2-Pyridyl	197	71
2d	3-Pyridyl	111	70
2e	4-Pyridyl	197	50

* Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained.

Experimental

Preparation of 4-benzoyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl) isoxazole (2a): A mixture of 3-benzoyl-2-(4-chlorophenyl) chromone (1.7 g), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3 g) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The resulting solid after cooling and on addition of excess of water, was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (50%), m.p. 145° (Found: C, 70; H, 3.2; N, 3.3. C₂₂H₁₄NO₃Cl calcd for: C, 70.4; H, 3.7; N, 3.7%). Purity of 2a was checked by tlc.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. V. Kaulgud, Head, Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University for facilities.

References

1. K. A. THAKAR and V. N. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 571.
2. M. M. OHINCHOLKAR and V. S. JAMODR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 18, 510; *Acta Oenica Indica, Ser. Chem.*, 1988, 9, 28 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1984, 101, 110789).

Synthesis of Steroidal Extranucleo Thiazolidones of Cholestane Series

A. H. SIDDIQUI*, K. VENKATESHWER RAO

and

R. KESHAVA RAO

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College, Hyderabad-500 001

Manuscript received 6 April 1988, accepted 1 September 1988

THIAZOLIDONES have been found to be endowed with a variety of biological activities¹. The ketones, 6-oxo-5 α -cholestan-3 β -yl acetate² (1a) and 3-oxo-5-cholestene³ (2a) were reacted with hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic solution to obtain the corresponding hydrazones (1b, 2b); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300, 3 200 (NH₂) and 1 425, 1 415 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The compound (1b, 2b) when refluxed with ammonium thiocyanate in benzene solution gave the respective thiosemicarbazones (1c, 2c); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300, 3 150 (NH₂) and 1 125 cm⁻¹ (C=S).

1a; X=O
1b; X=NNH₂
1c; X=NNHOSNH₂

2a; X=O
2b; X=NNH₂
2c; X=NNHOSNH₂

3a

3b

4a

4b

The cyclisation of (1c, 2c) with chloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished 6-diazo-5 α -cholestan-6-(1',3'-thiazolidan-4'-one)-3 β -yl acetate (3a) and 3-diazo-5-cholesten-3-(1',3'-thiazolidan-4'-one) (4a), respectively; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300 (NH), 1 715 (C=O of thiazolidone) and 1 425, 1 415 cm⁻¹ (C=C, C=N); δ 7.8 (1H, s, NH, disappeared on addition of D₂O) and 5.4 (2H, s, CH₂ of thiazolidone); ¹³C nmr δ 220 (C=O of thiazolidone), 160 (C=N) and 73 (CH₂ of thiazolidone). The alternate structures (3b, 4b) are precluded on the basis of ¹³C nmr spectra as they are expected to show the signal for CH₂ of thiazolidone at δ 90.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, PMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and the ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL JNN FX-100 (25.00 Mz) spectrometer (temp., 25°) using TMS as internal standard.

Hydrazones (1b, 2b): The ketone (1a, 2a; 1.75 g) was refluxed with freshly distilled hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) in ethanolic (35 ml) in the presence of acetic acid (1 drop) for 2 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the residual solution was poured into ice-cold water. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried, and recrystallised from ethanol (1b, 2b; 1.55 g) (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		
			O	H	N
1b	147	C ₂₈ H ₅₀ N ₂ O ₂	76.02 (75.98)	10.98 (10.91)	6.23 (6.11)
2b	158-59	C ₂₇ H ₄₈ N ₂	81.56 (81.61)	11.85 (11.83)	7.16 (7.05)
1c	120-22	C ₂₈ H ₅₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	65.89 (65.81)	9.25 (9.32)	7.53 (7.67)
2c	190-92	C ₂₇ H ₄₉ N ₃ S	73.78 (73.68)	10.06 (10.08)	9.27 (9.20)
3a	104-06	C ₂₈ H ₅₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	68.75 (68.94)	9.23 (9.15)	7.52 (7.54)
4a	134-36	C ₂₈ H ₄₉ N ₃ OS	72.67 (72.58)	9.23 (9.27)	8.52 (8.46)

Thiosemicarbazones (1c, 2c): To the compound (1b, 2b; 2 g) in benzene (100 ml) was added ammonium thiocyanate (2 g), and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The excess benzene was then distilled off and the concentrated solution cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol to yield the product (1c, 2c; 1.65 g) (Table 1).

Thiazolidone (3a, 4a): The thiosemicarbazone (1c, 2c; 1 g) was refluxed with chloroacetic acid (0.3 g) in presence of sodium acetate (0.4 g) and acetic acid (30 ml) for 6-8 h. The excess solvent